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Abstract

The monocationic chloro complexes containing chelating NNN ligands: $[(\eta^6\text{-p-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{L}1\text{-}4)\text{Cl}]^+$ (1-4), where L1 = 4-methyl-1,10-phenanthroline, L2 = dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine, L3 = 11-chloro-dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine, L4 = 11-nitro-dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine; p-cymene = 1-methyl-4-isopropylbenzene) have been prepared and characterized as the hexafluorophosphate salts. The biological activity of 1-4 has been investigated in selected 2D monolayer cell cultures (A549, PANC-1, MDA-MB-231, MRC-5). All investigated ruthenium complexes showed similar or even better cytotoxicity to cisplatin. However, there was no significant reduction in growth of PANC-1 cells in a 3D cell culture of multicellular tumor spheroids (MCTS) after treatment with 2-4, while the cisplatin treatment induced retardation in MCTS growth. Flow cytometry analysis of the cell cycle of PANC-1 cells shows that 3 caused changes of cell cycle phase distribution characterized by slight accumulation of cells in the G2-M phase. Absence of the Sub-G1 phase in the cell cycle of the treated cells indicated that there was no fragmentation of DNA for the analyzed time intervals (48 and 72 h treatment). Fluorescent microscopy, after acridine orange/ethidium bromide staining, revealed that the investigated ruthenium complexes induced some characteristics of apoptotic morphology (shrinking and condensation of chromatin) with notably preserved integrity of the plasma membrane. Investigation of cellular uptake and DNA - fraction accumulation performed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry in PANC-1 cells with equimolar concentrations (5 μM) of 2-4 and cisplatin showed more efficient cellular uptake and DNA - fraction accumulation of complex 3 compared to complexes 2 and 4.

Keywords	Organoruthenium complexes, Crystal structure, 3D cell culture, Cytotoxicity
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For Prof. John H. Dawson, PhD
Editor-in-Chief of Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry

July 30th, 2019

Dear Prof. Dawson,

Please find enclosed our manuscript entitled:

**“Antitumor activity of organoruthenium complexes with chelate aromatic ligands,
derived from 1,10-phenantroline: synthesis and biological activity”**

by the authors

Aleksandar Savić, Nevenka Gligorijević, Sandra Arandelović, Biljana Dojčinović, Anna M. Kaczmarek, Siniša Radulović, Rik Van Deun, Kristof Van Hecke which we would like to be considered for publication in the Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry.

This is an original paper which has never been published before or sent for publishing to any other journal.

The enclosed manuscript refers to the chemical and biological study of organoruthenium(II) complexes with chelate aromatic ligands, derived from 1,10-phenantroline ligands. From strictly chemical point of view, the study includes syntheses, full characterization (including the conformation of proposed structures using single-crystal X-ray diffraction analyses) of reported complexes. Also, their biological activity on 2D and 3D models was described in detail.

Yours sincerely,

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- Synthesis, characterization and biological evaluation of organoruthenium complexes
- Crystallographic analysis confirms a piano-stool geometry of complexes.
- Investigation of antitumor activity on 2D and 3D cell cultures.
- High cytotoxicity of investigated compounds, even higher than cisplatin.

1

2

3

Compound	IC ₅₀ (μM)				
	K562	A549	PANC-1	MDA-MB-231	MRC-5
1	6.65±0.07	26.85±7.67	21.26±0.98	7.44±2.75	4.23±0.63
2	6.23±2.26	19.45±3.37	5.49±0.64	5.60±0.03	8.62±3.61
3	6.35±1.51	9.23±1.40	8.47±2.21	9.06±4.48	13.92±4.04

Antitumor activity of organoruthenium complexes with chelate aromatic ligands, derived from 1,10-phenantroline: synthesis and biological activity

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Abstract:

The monocationic chloro complexes containing chelating NNN ligands: $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{L1-4})\text{Cl}]^+$ (**1-4**), where L1 = 4-methyl-1,10-phenantroline, L2 = dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine, L3 = 11-chloro-dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine, L4 = 11-nitro-dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine; *p*-cymene = 1-methyl-4-isopropylbenzene) have been prepared and characterized as the hexafluorophosphate salts. The biological activity of **1-4** has been investigated in selected 2D monolayer cell cultures (A549, PANC-1, MDA-MB-231, MRC-5). All investigated ruthenium complexes showed similar or even better cytotoxicity to *cisplatin*. However, there was no significant reduction in growth of PANC-1 cells in a 3D cell culture of multicellular tumor spheroids (MCTS) after treatment with **2-4**, while the *cisplatin* treatment induced retardation in MCTS growth. Flow cytometry analysis of the cell cycle of PANC-1 cells shows that **3** caused changes of cell cycle phase distribution characterized by slight accumulation of cells in the G2-M phase. Absence of the Sub-G1 phase in the cell cycle of the treated cells indicated that there was no fragmentation of DNA for the analyzed time intervals (48 and 72 h treatment). Fluorescent microscopy, after acridine orange/ethidium bromide staining, revealed that the investigated ruthenium complexes induced some characteristics of apoptotic morphology (shrinking and condensation of chromatin) with notably preserved integrity of the plasma membrane. Investigation of cellular uptake and DNA - fraction accumulation performed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry in PANC-1 cells with equimolar concentrations (5 μM) of **2-4** and *cisplatin* showed more efficient cellular uptake and DNA - fraction accumulation of complex **3** compared to complexes **2** and **4**.

Keywords: Organoruthenium complexes, Crystal structure, 3D cell culture, cytotoxicity.

1. Introduction:

A modern era of metal-based anticancer drugs began with Rosenberg's discovery of *cisplatin* [1]. Thousands of platinum complexes have been synthesized in attempt to discover more effective anti-tumor drugs, however only a small number of these compounds have entered clinical trials. Nowadays, *cisplatin*, *carboplatin* and *oxaliplatin* are used in about 50% of all cancer treatments [2-4]. A main limitation of these platinum drugs is development of resistance to their action, due to the multiple mechanism including inactivation in tumor cells by small molecules (*e.g.* glutathione) and ejection from the cells or due to malfunction of cellular DNA damage response or apoptotic mechanisms [5, 6]. Also, numerous side effects (nausea, vomiting, nephro-, neuro- and ototoxicity) are frequently observed in clinical application of the mentioned drugs [3]. The major task in metal-based anticancer drug design nowadays is surpassing *cisplatin* effectiveness and overcoming *cisplatin* resistance. Because of the complexity of this issue and the number of affecting factors, this has led to a large number of different approaches to the problem. One that has been attractive in the previous three decades is the design of ruthenium based anticancer complexes. Ruthenium complexes possess unique physicochemical properties, which make them very promising as anticancer agents, *i.e.* (a) activation by reduction from inactive Ru(III) to active Ru(II) in tumor cells, where more hypoxic and acidic conditions exist; (b) different geometry of the ligands environment (tetrahedral or octahedral), which leads to design of complexes with a specific cellular target (*e.g.* proteins, DNA); (c) favorable ligand-exchange kinetics; (d) ability to interact with transferrin receptors and in that way accumulate in tumor cells. Also, the ability of ruthenium to mimic iron in transferrin, leads to lower systemic toxicity, compared with platinum complexes [7-17]. Structural diversity of ruthenium compounds has yielded different families of ruthenium antitumor agents, with different mode of actions governed by their redox potential and their relative lipophilicity/hydrophilicity, which determines their cellular uptake [11, 18, 19]. In the literature, there are many proposed mechanisms which describe

antitumor activity of ruthenium complexes: interaction with DNA [20], inhibition of kinases [21] or topoisomerases [22] inhibition of the cell cycle [23], and induction of mitochondrial dysfunction pathways [24]. Several ruthenium drugs display promising antitumor activity combined with lower toxicity in relevant *in vivo* models. The first ruthenium complexes, which have reached the farthest in biological investigations and entered clinical trial, are Ru(III) complexes NAMI-A and KP1339 (including its sodium salt NKP-1339 (currently IT-139) [25]. Ruthenium (II) polypyridyl complexes of structural formula $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2\text{dppz}]^{2+}$ or $[\text{Ru}(\text{phen})_2\text{dppz}]^{2+}$, with different functional groups on the dppz ligand, demonstrated potential ability for the medical application, as photosensitizers [26, 27]. The most successful PDT photosensitizer to date is TLD-1433 which phase Ib clinical trials was completed last year [28]. Ruthenium complexes containing heterocyclic base molecules have shown promising antitumor properties. For example, it was found that the complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})(\text{phpy})(\text{dppz})]^+$ (phpy = 2-phenylpyridine, dppz = dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine) (Fig. 1a) was rapidly taken up by cancer cells with 90% of the complex accumulated in the nuclei of cancer cells [29, 30], while $[\text{Ru}(\text{dppz})_2(\text{CppH})]^{2+}$ (CppH = 2-(2-pyridyl)pyrimidine-4-carboxylic acid) (Fig. 1b) specifically targeted mitochondria and exhibited cytotoxicity comparable to *cisplatin* in HeLa cells [30, 31]. Also, it has been observed that the cytotoxicity of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{N-N})]\text{Cl}_2$ complexes, where N-N is bpy = 2,2'-bipyridyl (Fig. 1c) or phen = 1,10-phenanthroline, (Fig. 1d) or dpq = pyrazino[2,3-f] [1,10]phenanthroline (Fig. 1e) or dppz = dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine (Fig. 1f) or dppn (4,5,9,16-tetraaza-dibenzo[a,c]naphthacen) (Fig. 1g), was increasing with the size of the aromatic moiety, with drastically lowering IC_{50} value for $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dppn})]^{2+}$ complex [32].

Figure 1. Structures of some ruthenium complexes with heterocyclic aromatic base as ligands: a) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})(\text{phpy})(\text{dppz})]^+$ (phpy = 2-phenylpyridine, dppz = dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine); b) $[\text{Ru}(\text{dppz})_2(\text{CppH})]^{2+}$ (CppH = 2-(2-pyridyl)pyrimidine-4-carboxylic acid); c) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ (bpy = 2,2'-bipyridyl); d) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{phen})]^{2+}$ (phen = 1,10-phenanthroline); e) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dpq})]^{2+}$ (dpq = pyrazino[2,3-f][1,10]phenanthroline); f) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dppz})]^{2+}$ (dppz = dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine); g) $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_2(\text{dppn})]^{2+}$ (dppn = 4,5,9,16-tetraaza-dibenzo[a,c] naphthacen).

Organoruthenium complexes of the type $[(\eta^6\text{-arene})\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{XY})\text{Z}]^+$ (where YZ is an N,N-, N,O-, O,O- or S,O-chelating ligand, and X is a monoanionic ligand) are highly cytotoxic and reduce tumor growth *in vivo*. The arene ligands are strongly coordinated to the ruthenium, stabilize this metal in oxidation state +2 and provide a hydrophobic side for the passive transport

through cell membranes [33-36]. Coordination of N,N'-chelating ligands to organoruthenium(II)- species, resulted in cytotoxicity comparable to that of *cisplatin* in a number of cell lines, including *cisplatin*-resistant cell lines [37].

Traditional research on the efficacy of anticancer drugs is most often performed in two-dimensional (2-D) cell cultures, which may not be a genuine indicator of the *in vivo* effectiveness [38]. Some experimental drugs may be exclusively effective in cancer cell monolayers but not-effective in solid tumors [39, 40]. The multicellular tumor spheroids (MSTC) are micro-sized cellular aggregates that have been widely used to assemble 3D culture models of different cancer types *in vitro* and are able to mimic various features of solid tumors [41]. Recently, investigation of the mechanism of action of half-sandwich Ru(II)-arene complexes of the type $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{Me}_2\text{dppz})\text{Cl}]\text{PF}_6$, has revealed that this compound acts as strong cytotoxic agent with potential of efficient cellular accumulation and ability of binding nuclear DNA with a much higher affinity than *cisplatin* [42]. In this study, we synthesized a class of organoruthenium complexes with derivatized 1,10-phenanthroline ligands, studied their structure-activity relationship and revealed the changes in biological activity resulting from structural modifications of the synthesized Ru(II) complexes.

The MCTS more accurately provide insight into the metabolic properties similar to solid tumor profiles such as nutrient and oxygen gradients, hypoxic/necrotic regions, cell-cell interactions and gene expression [39, 43-45]. Hence, a 3D model was introduced in our research to investigate the efficacy of novel ruthenium complexes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemistry

RuCl₃·xH₂O, 4-methyl-1-(1-methylethyl)-1,3-cyclohexadiene, 4-methyl-1,10-phenanthroline, potassium-bromate, *o*-phenylenediamine, 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine, 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine and NH₄PF₆ were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, while the solvents were obtained from different commercial sources and used as received. 1,10-Phenanthroline-5,6-dione [46] and the ligands dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine [47], 11-nitrodipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine [48] and 11-chlorodipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine [48] were synthesized according to literature procedures with slight modifications.

Elemental analysis (C, H, N) was carried out with a Thermo Scientific Flash 2000 Series CHNS/O Analyzer. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance 500 MHz and all chemical shifts are given relative to tetramethylsilane (TMS). Standard LC-MS analysis was performed on an Agilent 1100 series HPLC equipped with quaternary pump and UV-DAD detection, directly coupled to an Agilent G1956B single quadrupole MS detector equipped with an ESI ionization source. High resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) was performed on an Agilent 1100 series HPLC equipped with a quaternary pump and UV-DAD detector directly coupled to an Agilent 6220A series Time-of-Flight MS detector, equipped with an ESI/APCI (multimode) ionization source. IR spectra were recorded from 4000 to 650 cm⁻¹, on a Thermo Scientific FT-IR spectrometer (type Nicolet 6700), using KBr as a non-absorbing matrix.

Single-crystal X-ray diffraction measurements were performed on a Rigaku Oxford Diffraction Supernova Dual Source (Cu at zero) diffractometer equipped with an Atlas CCD detector using ω scans and CuK α ($\lambda = 1.54178 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. Samples were cooled during the measurement by an Oxford Instruments Cryojet5 LN₂ cryocooling at 100 K. All images were interpreted and integrated with the program CrysAlisPro (Rigaku Oxford Diffraction) [49]. Using Olex2 [50], the structures were solved by direct methods using the ShelXS structure

solution program [51] and refined by full-matrix least squares on F^2 using the ShelXL program [51, 52].

2.2. Biology

2.2.1. Cell culture

The human lung carcinoma cells (A549), human pancreatic carcinoma cells (PANC-1), breast cancer cells (MDA-MB-231) and human fetal lung fibroblast cells (MRC-5) were maintained as monolayer culture in the Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 nutrient medium (Sigma Chemicals Co, USA). The human myelogenous leukemia cells (K562) were maintained in suspension culture. RPMI 1640 nutrient medium was prepared in sterile ionized water, supplemented with penicillin (100 IU/mL), streptomycin (200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), 4-(2-hydroxyethyl)piperazine-1-ethanesulfonic acid (HEPES) (25 mM), L-glutamine (3 mM) and 10% of heat-inactivated fetal calf serum (FCS) (pH 7.2). The cells were grown at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO_2 .

2.2.2. MTT assay

The cytotoxicity of the investigated complexes (**1-4**), and cisplatin (as reference compound) was determined using the 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT, Sigma) assay as previously described [53]. Briefly, 24 h after seeding the cells into 96-well cell culture plates (Thermo Scientific Nunc™), the cells were exposed to the investigated complexes. The complexes were dissolved in DMSO at a concentration of 10 mM and afterwards diluted in culture medium to the desired concentrations. The final DMSO concentration never exceeded 1% (v/v). After an incubation period of 72 h, 20 μL of MTT solution (5 mg/mL in phosphate buffer, pH 7.2) was added to each well. Samples were incubated for 4 h at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO_2 , and then 100 μL of 10% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) was added. Absorbance was recorded after 24 h, on an enzyme

linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) reader (Thermo Labsystems Multiskan EX 200-240 V), at the wavelength of 570 nm. The IC₅₀ value, defined as the concentration of the compound causing 50% cell growth inhibition, was determined from the cell survival diagrams.

2.2.3. Cell cycle analysis

Analysis of the cell cycle phase distribution of PANC-1 cells after treatment with complexes (2-4), showing the most prominent cytotoxicity, was performed by flow-cytometric analysis of the DNA content after staining with propidium iodide (PI) [54]. The cells were seeded at a density of 2×10^5 cells per well, into 6-well plates (Thermo Scientific Nunc™), in the nutrition medium. The cells were continually exposed to the investigated ruthenium complex 2-4 or CDDP at concentrations corresponding to IC₅₀^{72 h}. Control cells were incubated only in a nutrient medium or nutrition medium with DMSO. After 24 h or 48 h of growth, the cells were collected, washed twice with ice-cold phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and fixed overnight, in 70% ethanol. After fixation, the cells were washed with PBS, and incubated with RNaseA (1 mg/mL) for 30 min, at 37 °C. Immediately before flow-cytometric analysis, the cells were stained with PI, at a concentration of 400 µg/mL. Samples were analyzed using a fluorescence activated cell sorter (FACS), by Calibur Becton Dickinson flow cytometer, at 488 nm excitation line (Argon-ion laser). The data were analyzed by Cell Quest computer software.

2.2.4. Morphological analysis of cell death by fluorescent microscopy

The PANC-1 cells (1×10^5) were seeded on coverslips into 6-well plates (ThermoScientific Nunc™) in 2 mL of the nutrient medium. After 24 h of growth, the cells were treated with the investigated complexes or CDDP, at 0.5 x IC₅₀ or $1 \times$ IC₅₀ concentrations. Following 48 h and 72 h of treatment, the cells were stained with ethidium bromide (3 µg/mL) and acridine

orange (5 µg/mL), according to standard procedures [55, 56], and immediately after, observed under the fluorescent microscope – Carl Zeiss PALM MicroBeam with Axio Observer.Z1 using AxioCam MRm (filters Alexa Fluor 489 and Alexa Fluor 546) using the Zeiss Fluor 10×/0.50 or LD Plan-NeoFluar 20×/0.4 objectives. Images were obtained with multidimensional acquisition using digital imaging software (AxioVision Version 4.7; Carl Zeiss Imaging Solutions).

2.2.5. Generation and analysis of MCTSs.

The multicellular tumor spheroids (MCTS) comprised exclusively of PANC-1 cells were cultured using the low attachment U96-well plate Thermo Scientific Nunclon Sphera (Nunclon Sphera 96 well U bottom plates). PANC-1 cells in the exponential growth phase were dissociated by a trypsin/EDTA solution to gain single-cell suspensions. A number of 500 cells/well (1000 cells/well) were transferred to 96-well plates with 200 µL of DMEM containing 10% serum. The single cells formed MCTS aggregates approximately 500 µm (or minimum 500 µm) in diameter after five days with 5% CO₂ and 20% O₂ at 37 °C. The formation and growth of spheroids were examined using an Invitrogen™ EVOS FLC™ imaging system. The PANC-1 spheroids pre-selected for homogeneous volume and shape were treated by carefully replacing 50 µL of the medium with drug-supplemented standard medium. Three PANC-1 MCTSs were treated per condition and drug concentration.

The live/dead analysis of PANC-1 cells MCTSs was performed using two types of dual fluorescent staining: 1) Calcein-AM (Sigma-Aldrich) and PI (Sigma-Aldrich) staining and 2) the Thermo Fisher LIVE/DEAD (Blue/Green). In Calcein-AM and PI dual staining the live cells were distinguished by the presence of ubiquitous intracellular esterase activity, as determined by enzymatic conversion of the virtually non-fluorescent cell-permeant Calcein-AM to the intensely fluorescent Calcein. PI enter only cells with damaged membranes and

show fluorescence upon binding to nucleic acids, thereby producing a red fluorescence in dead cells. Briefly, after treatment with the complexes, the MCTSs were incubated with Calcein-AM (3 μ M) and PI (5 μ M) solutions for 30 min and imaged directly using an Invitrogen™ EVOS FLC™ imaging system.

In a separate experiment using another type of staining Thermo Fisher LIVE/DEAD (Blue/Green) after treatment with the complexes, the MCTSs were incubated with staining solution, which was made according to the manufacturer's procedure. Briefly, 2 drops of each at room temperature, stable NucBlue® Live reagent (Hoechst 33342) and NucGreen® Dead reagent were added to 1 mL of cell growth media. NucBlue® Live reagent stains the nuclei of all the cells and it was detected with a standard DAPI filter. NucGreen® Dead reagent stains only the nuclei of cells with compromised plasma membrane integrity and was detected using a standard GFP (green) filter.

2.2.6. Cellular uptake and DNA-binding by ICP-MS

The cellular uptake of ruthenium complexes (**2-4**) and cisplatin after 24 h treatment of PANC-1 cells was investigated by measuring the intracellular ruthenium or platinum level by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), using a Thermo Scientific iCAP Qc ICP-MS (Thermo Scientific, Bremen, Germany) spectrometer with operational software Qtegra. The instrument was optimized and the external standards for the instrument calibration were prepared according to the previously described procedure [42]. PANC-1 cells (1.5×10^6) were seeded into 75 cm² dishes (Thermo Scientific Nunc™), and at the exponential phase of growth, the cells were treated with complexes **2-4** or CDDP at equimolar concentrations of 5 μ M. After 24 h of drug treatment, the cells were rinsed with PBS, detached with trypsin and counted. The cell pellet was collected by centrifugation at 2000 rpm, 10 min.

Likewise, PANC-1 cells were prepared, and the cell pellet collected using the same procedure as described above for the measurement of DNA-binding using ICP-MS. The total DNA was isolated using TRI Reagent® (Sigma Aldrich), according to the manufacturer's procedure and concentrations were determined spectrophotometrically by measuring absorbances (Eppendorf BioPhotometer 6131).

3. Experimental part

3.1. Synthesis of the ligands

The precursor ligand, 1,10-phenanthroline-5,6-dione was synthesized by oxidation of 1,10-phenanthroline with potassium bromate and 65% (v/v) sulphuric acid at room temperature (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 1,10-phenanthroline-5,6-dione.

Dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine (dppz), 11-nitrodipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine (11-NO₂-dppz) and 11-chlorodipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine (11-Cl-dppz) (Scheme 2) were synthesized in reaction between 1,10-phenanthroline-5,6-dione and *o*-phenylene diamine or 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine or 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine, respectively, in 96% (v/v) methanol (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Synthesis of the (un)substituted dppz ligands: L2-L4.

3.2. Synthesis of the complexes

3.2.1. [(*p*-cymene)Ru(L1)Cl]PF₆ (1)

To a suspension of 36.74 mg (0.06 mmol) [(η^6 -*p*-cymene)Ru(μ -Cl)Cl]₂ in a mixture of methanol/chloroform (15 mL, 1:1), a solution of 23.29 mg (0.12 mmol) of 4-methyl-1,10-phenanthroline in methanol (5 mL) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at 40 °C during 4 h. Then, the orange solution was concentrated under reduced pressure to *ca.* 7 mL, solid NH₄PF₆ was added 29.34 mg (0.18 mmol) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. A yellow-orange precipitate appeared after cooling the solution overnight at 4 °C, was collected with filtration and washed with methanol (2 × 2.5 mL). Orange crystals, suitable for X-ray diffraction, were obtained from the mother liquor at room temperature. Yield: 53 mg (77%). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₃H₂₄ClF₆N₂PRu, %: C 45.29, H 3.97, N 4.59. Found, %: C 44.89, H 3.40, N 4.51. HRMS: [M]⁺ calcd. for. C₂₃H₂₄ClN₂Ru⁺, 465.0666; found: 465.0645. IR (KBr): 3066.2, 2974.7, 2935.5, 2880.0, 1628.9, 1603.0, 1585.9, 1573.1, 1541.9, 1508.6, 1466.0, 1432.3, 1382.2, 1229.8, 1141.0, 1094.3, 1057.2, 1030.3, 1012.5, 908.1, 875.3, 820.4, 775.8, 728.7. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm: 0.90 (d, 6H), 2.18 (s, 3H), 2.61 (sept, 1H), 2.98 (s, 3H), 6.09 (t, 2H), 6.32 (t, 2H), 8.03 (d, 1H), 8.16 (m, 1H), 8.31 (d, 1H),

8.35 (d, 1H), 8.93 (d, 1H), 9.77 (dd, 1H) and 9.92 (dd, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ ppm: 18.70, 18.74, 22.09, 22.11, 30.85, 84.08, 84.22, 86.34, 86.38, 103.15, 104.20, 124.95, 126.73, 127.38, 127.53, 130.13, 130.27, 139.13, 145.18, 145.76, 149.75, 155.68, 156.46.

3.2.2. [(*p*-cymene)Ru(L2)Cl]PF₆ (2)

To a suspension of 24.49 mg (0.04 mmol) [(η^6 -cymene)Ru(μ -Cl)Cl]₂ in a mixture of methanol/chloroform (15 mL, 1:1), a solution of 22.58 mg (0.08 mmol) of dipyrido[3,2-*a*:2',3'-*c*]phenazine (dppz) in methanol (5 mL) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at 40 °C during 4 h. Then, the orange solution was concentrated under reduced pressure to *ca.* 7 mL, solid NH₄PF₆ was added 19.56 mg (0.12 mmol) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. A yellow-orange precipitate appeared after cooling the solution overnight at 4 °C, was collected with filtration and washed with methanol (2 × 2.5 mL). Orange crystals, suitable for X-ray diffraction, were obtained by slow diffusion of diethyl ether into the mother liquor at room temperature. Yield: 34 mg (61%). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₄ClF₆N₄PRu, %: C 48.18, H 3.47, N 8.03. Found, %: C 48.05, H 3.14, N 7.71. HRMS: [M]⁺ calcd. for C₂₈H₂₄ClN₄Ru⁺, 553.0728; found: 553.0733. IR (KBr): 3083.0, 2966.0, 1604.3, 1497.3, 1470.8, 1447.3, 1422.9, 1390.9, 1357.3, 1342.8, 1139.1, 1093.5, 1079.7, 1052.5, 879.0, 859.0, 818.0, 802.5, 767.4, 727.9. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : 1.01 (d, 6H), 2.23 (s, 3H), 2.71 (sept, 1H), 6.17 (d, 2H), 6.40 (d, 2H), 8.14 (m, 2H), 8.31 (m, 2H), 8.44 (m, 2H), 9.71 (d, 2H), and 10.02 (dd, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ ppm: 18.72, 22.24, 30.93, 84.70, 86.41, 103.24, 105.29, 128.12, 129.88, 129.95, 133.03, 135.82, 139.74, 142.41, 148.47, 157.80.

3.2.3. [(*p*-cymene)Ru(L3)Cl]PF₆ (3)

To a suspension of 25.03 mg (0.04 mmol) $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}(\mu\text{-Cl})\text{Cl}]_2$ in a mixture of methanol/chloroform (15 mL, 1:1), a solution of 25.34 mg (0.08 mmol) of 11-chlorodipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine (Cl-dppz) in methanol (5 mL) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at 40 °C during 4 h. Then, the orange solution was concentrated under reduced pressure to *ca.* 7 mL, solid NH_4PF_6 was added 21.19 mg (0.13 mmol) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. A yellow-orange precipitate appeared after cooling the solution overnight at 4 °C, was collected with filtration and washed with methanol (2 × 2.5 mL). Orange crystals, suitable for X-ray diffraction, were obtained by slow diffusion of diethyl ether in the mother liquor at room temperature. Yield 34 mg (58%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{23}\text{Cl}_2\text{F}_6\text{N}_4\text{PRu}$, %: C 45.92, H 3.17, N 7.65. Found, %: C 45.43, H 2.98, N 7.07. HRMS: $[\text{M}]^+$ calcd. for. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{23}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{Ru}^+$, 587.0338; found: 587.0322. IR (KBr): 3125.4, 2964.6, 1597.7, 1494.6, 1473.1, 1445.4, 1414.3, 1391.4, 1354.0, 1141.4, 1080.9, 1062.1, 933.1, 841.8, 779.1, 742.6, 726.8. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, acetone- d_6) δ ppm: 1.14 (d, 6H), 2.36 (s, 3H), 2.90 (sept, 1H), 6.21 (d, 2H), 6.44 (d, 2H), 8.17 (d, 1H), 8.38 (m, 2H), 8.50 (m, 2H), 9.83 (m, 2H), and 10.02 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, acetone- d_6) δ ppm: 18.86, 22.31, 31.91, 85.53, 87.05, 104.26, 106.90, 128.63, 129.06, 132.27, 134.15, 136.62, 138.67, 141.22, 149.68, 158.25.

3.2.4. $[(p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{L4})\text{Cl}]\text{PF}_6$ (4)

To a suspension of 30.60 mg (0.05 mmol) $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}(\mu\text{-Cl})\text{Cl}]_2$ in a mixture of methanol/chloroform (15 mL, 1:1), a solution of 32.73 mg (0.10 mmol) of 11-nitrodipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine (NO_2 -dppz) in methanol (5 mL) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at 40 °C during 4 h. Then, the orange solution was concentrated under reduced pressure to *ca.* 7 mL, solid NH_4PF_6 was added 24.48 mg (0.15 mmol) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. A yellow-orange precipitate appeared after cooling

the solution overnight at 4 °C, was collected with filtration and washed with methanol (2 × 2.5 mL). Yield 40 mg (54%). Anal. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₃ClF₆N₅O₂PRu, %: C 45.26, H 3.12, N 9.43. Found, %: C 45.45, H 2.86, N 9.59. HRMS: [M]⁺ calcd. for. C₂₈H₂₃ClN₅O₂Ru⁺, 598.0573; found: 598.0573. IR (KBr): 3093.5, 2970.6, 1608.5, 1523.8, 1495.3, 1419.3, 1349.1, 1073.6, 1051.7, 877.2, 844.3, 745.0, 738.5, 729.4. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm: 1.00 (d, 6H), 2.22 (s, 3H), 2.70 (sept, 1H), 6.17 (d, 2H), 6.41 (d, 2H), 8.33 (m, 2H), 8.66 and 8.78 (d, 1H and dd 1H), 9.24 (d, 1H), 9.72 (dd, 2H), and 10.05 (dd, 2H). ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ ppm: 20.30, 23.80, 32.48, 86.26, 87.98, 104.96, 106.96, 127.44, 129.92, 131.16, 133.48, 137.89, 142.55, 143.96, 145.73, 150.60, 160.0.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Synthesis and characterization of the complexes **1-4**.

By exploring the μ -chlorido-bridge splitting reaction of $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})\text{RuCl}_2]_2$ with L1-L4 in methanol/chloroform at 40 °C, with subsequent addition of ammonium hexafluorophosphate, complexes (**1-4**), general formula, $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{L})\text{Cl}]^+\text{PF}_6^-$, have been prepared in good yields (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. Synthesis of the complexes 1-4.

Complex **2** has already been described in the literature, however, antitumor activity and crystal structure for **2** have not been reported yet. All complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, mass spectrometry, IR and NMR spectroscopy. Also, complexes **1**, **2** and **3** were characterized by X-ray crystallography.

IR spectra of all complexes showed characteristic bands in at the following positions of wave numbers: around 3100 cm^{-1} (C–H stretching vibrations), 1600-1585 and 1500-1400 cm^{-1} (C–C and C–N stretching vibrations in the ring, respectively) and 900-675 cm^{-1} (out-of-plane bands).

The ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the complexes showed characteristic resonances of η^6 -*p*-cymene and the heterocyclic base moiety. Upon complexation to the metal, the symmetry of the ligand environment is lowered. This is observed in the cymene ring protons which appear as two doublets in the range of 6.09-6.44 ppm, in contrast to the one signal observed in [$(\eta^6$ -*p*-

cymene)RuCl₂]₂. The characteristic septet at 2.70 or 2.90 ppm is assigned to one proton from the isopropyl group of the *p*-cymene moiety. Signals in the range of 0.90-1.14 ppm and 2.18-2.36 ppm correspond to protons from -CH(CH₃)₂ and CH₃(arene) of the *p*-cymene. All signals originated from the heterocyclic base moiety were found in the region of 8.03-10.05 ppm.

The mass spectra of **1-4** recorded in acetonitrile contain peaks assigned to the [M⁺-PF₆⁻] ions, which agrees with their calculated molecular mass. Molecular ions of the complexes were detectable with *m/z* at 465.0645 for **1**, *m/z* at 553.0733 for **2**, *m/z* at 587.0322 for **3** and *m/z* at 598.0573 for **4**.

X-ray diffraction studies for **1-3** showed a common "piano-stool geometry", with coordination of the heterocyclic base ligands through the nitrogen donor atoms.

Compound **1** and **2** both crystallized in the monoclinic centrosymmetric space group *P*2₁/*c*. The asymmetric unit of **1** consists of one [(η⁶-*p*-cymene)Ru(L1)Cl]⁺ complex and one PF₆⁻ counterion, while for **2**, the asymmetric unit contains two [(η⁶-*p*-cymene)Ru(L2)Cl]⁺ complexes, two PF₆⁻ counterions and one co-crystallized diethyl ether solvent molecule. Compound **3** crystallized in the non-centrosymmetric orthorhombic space group *Pnc*2 with three [(η⁶-*p*-cymene)Ru(L3)Cl]⁺ complexes, two complete PF₆⁻ and two half's of PF₆⁻ (both on a 2-fold axis) counterions in the asymmetric unit.

For all three complexes, the Ru(II) center shows a pseudo-tetrahedral coordination by the *p*-cymene in a η⁶ mode, one Cl⁻ anion and the *N,N'*-chelating L ligands. The complexes all adopt the typical 'piano' stool conformation, which is illustrated by the N-Ru1-Cl1 angles of the complexes being in the range of 83.0(4)-86.28(7)°.

Figure 2. Molecular structures of **1** (a), **2** (b) and **3** (c), showing thermal displacement ellipsoids at the 50% and 30% probability levels for **1** and **2**, and **3**, respectively. Only one molecule of the asymmetric units is shown. PF_6^- counterions and the diethyl ether solvent molecule for compound **3** are omitted for clarity.

4.2. Results of MTT assay

The cytotoxic activity of the investigated ruthenium complexes, and *cisplatin* (as reference compound), against a panel of human cancer cell lines (K562, A549, PANC-1 and MDA-MB-231) and one normal cell line (MRC-5), was determined by an MTT assay. The activity was measured after 72 h incubation with the investigated complexes and the results are presented in Table 1 and Fig. 3. The remarkable high cytotoxicity with IC_{50} values ranging from 5 to 9 μM was revealed for complexes **2-4** against PANC-1 and MDA-MB-231 cells. The cytotoxicity of these complexes was about 2 to 3 times higher than that of *cisplatin*. Human myelogenous leukemia cells (K562) showed high sensitivity to all tested complexes with IC_{50} values being lower than *cisplatin* (up to 7 μM). Our results indicate that minor changes in the dppz ligand, like the introduction of a strongly electron-withdrawing group $-\text{NO}_2$ (**4**) or a weakly electron-withdrawing group $-\text{Cl}$ group (**3**), are not sufficient to induce important differences in cytotoxicity compared to the complex with unsubstituted dppz ligand (**2**). The complex with substituted phen ligand (**1**) also had notable activity on MDA-MB-231 cells (IC_{50} up to 7 μM , see Table 1).

Table 1. The cytotoxic activity of complexes **1-4** and *cisplatin* (CDDP) as reference compound determined after 72 h treatment by the MTT assay

Compound	IC ₅₀ (μM)				
	K562	A549	PANC-1	MDA-MB-231	MRC-5
1	6.65±0.07	26.85±7.67	21.26±0.98	7.44±2.75	4.23±0.63
2	6.23±2.26	19.45±3.37	5.49±0.64	5.60±0.03	8.62±3.61
3	6.35±1.51	9.23±1.40	8.47±2.21	9.06±4.48	13.92±4.04
4	6.77±1.86	18.89±2.08	5.66±0.37	5.41±0.57	9.98±1.85
<i>cisplatin</i>	10.86±0.55 ^b	5.93±0.66 ^a	16.44±1.56	14.54±0.05	10.54±0.21

IC₅₀ values were calculated as mean values obtained from two to three independent experiments and presented with their standard deviations. ^aResults of activity previously reported [57] ^bResults of activity previously reported [58]

Figure 3. Graphical representation of IC₅₀ values (μM) of the investigated ruthenium complexes and *cisplatin* on a panel of cell lines; each IC₅₀ value is the mean of two to three independent experiments with their corresponding SD.

4.3. Results of cell cycle analysis

The effect of complexes **2-4** and *cisplatin* on the cell cycle progression of PANC-1 cells was examined using propidium iodide (PI) staining and flow cytometry analysis. The results of the cell cycle analysis after treatment with concentrations corresponding to IC₅₀^{72 h} values (see Table 1) are determined at two points of time (48 h and 72 h) and presented in Fig. 4. After 48 h incubation, only complex **3** caused minor change of the cell cycle phase distribution, characterized by accumulation of cells in the G2-M phase (52.09% vs control 42.01%). After prolonged treatment (72 h), complex **3** caused further accumulation of cells in the G2 phase.

Minor accumulation of cells in the Sub-G1 phase, as characteristic of discontinuous fragmentation of nuclear DNA, was noticed only for *cisplatin*-treated cells. *Cisplatin*, after 48 h, induced blocking of the cell cycle in the S phase, which led to further increase of the percentage of cells in the sub-G1 phase determined after 72 h treatment.

Unique properties of transition metal complexes may allow specific interactions with DNA [59]. These interactions can arise due to covalent/coordinative or subtle non-coordinative interactions such as electrostatic attraction, groove binding and intercalation as well as combinations all these modes [59]. The dppz ligand in **2** allows extensive intercalative stacking in DNA base pairs. With few exceptions, most of the Ru-dppz complexes interact strongly to the DNA duplex through intercalation [60].

In a recent study in HeLa cells, flow cytometry analysis of cell cycle perturbation induced by a very similar ruthenium complex $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{Me}_2\text{dppz})\text{Cl}]\text{PF}_6$, revealed concentration- and time-dependent arrest of the cell cycle in G2-M and S phases. This event is followed by the accumulation of cells in sub-G1 phase after 48 h, in levels higher than *cisplatin* [42]. These changes in the cell cycle of HeLa cells strongly suggested direct DNA binding of this complex. While in the present study, absence of notable cell cycle perturbations (complexes **2** and **4**), and absence of Sub-G1 pik (complex **3**) in PANC-1 cells, may be explained by drug resistant and very complicated nature of pancreatic cancer cells [61]. Resistance mechanisms probably prevented DNA fragmentation characteristic for an apoptotic type of cell death. Results of morphological analysis of PANC-1 cell death, induced by complexes **2-4**, confirmed that only few characteristics of apoptosis were detected, and that further analysis is necessary for defining the accurate type of cell death.

A)

B)

Figure 4. Cell cycle phase distribution of PANC-1 cells, treated with complexes 2-4 or CDDP after A) 48 h and B) 72 h. Bar graphs show representative experiments of at least three independent experiments.

4.4. Results of cellular uptake and DNA-binding by ICP-MS

Nowadays, cellular uptake studies are becoming an essential part of the development and investigations of novel metal-based drugs. As DNA is being generally accepted as the critical target for platinum-based antitumor agents, DNA binding studies have become an integrative part of this type of research [62].

Cellular uptake and DNA binding of PANC-1 cells of the investigated ruthenium complexes **2-4** and *cisplatin* was determined by ICP-MS after 24 h treatment with 5 μ M concentrations of complexes (\sim IC₅₀) and *cisplatin*.

ICP-MS analysis revealed surprisingly more efficient cellular uptake of complex **3**, compared to complexes **2** and **4** (Fig. 5A). Intracellular accumulation of complex **3** (6492.90 ngRu/10⁶ cells) exceeded, six and ten times respectively, the level of intracellular accumulation of complex **2** (1069.97 ngRu/10⁶ cells), and complex **4** (675.06 ngRu/10⁶ cells). The results of the DNA binding demonstrated a similar trend, showing three to four times higher DNA binding of complex **3** (1.6 ngRu/ μ gDNA), compared to complex **2** (0.6 ngRu/ μ gDNA) and complex **4** (0.4 ngRu/ μ gDNA) (Fig. 5B). Enhanced intracellular uptake and DNA binding of complex **3**, apparently, are not directly proportional to its cytotoxicity in the 2D model system (see section results of MTT assay, Table 1). Complexes **2** and **4** showed rather similar level of intracellular uptake and slightly higher level of DNA binding, compared to *cisplatin*. Interactions of ruthenium complexes **2-4** with the DNA, are anticipated to be intercalative, due to the (un)substituted dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine ligand, which would be different to the known mechanism of *cisplatin* action [63].

Cisplatin showed considerably lower cellular uptake (653.93 ngPt/10⁶ cells) and DNA binding (0.2 ngPt/ μ gDNA), which is consistent to its poor cytotoxicity in PANC-1 cells, compared to ruthenium complexes **2-4**. Still, despite that fact, *cisplatin* action was demonstrated by induction of cell cycle arrest in the S phase, and appearance of sub-G1 pik (Fig. 4). Knowing that only 5-10% of *cisplatin* eventually form DNA-adducts in the cell, this allowed us to conclude that the poor **CDDP**-activity in PANC-1 cells is mainly due to the lower cellular uptake.

Our previous study of structurally related ruthenium complex ($[(\eta^6-p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{Me}_2\text{dppz})\text{Cl}]\text{PF}_6$), showed its ability to accumulate in HeLa cells more efficiently

than *cisplatin*. Results of the present study in **CDDP**-resistant PANC-1 cells, clearly demonstrate significantly higher intracellular uptake of ruthenium complex **3**.

A)

B)

Figure 5. ICP-MS analysis of ruthenium/platinum intracellular accumulation and DNA binding, in PANC-1 cells, after 24 h treatment, with 5 μ M of the investigated ruthenium complexes/*cisplatin*. A) Ru/Pt intracellular accumulation expressed as the ng Ru/10⁶ cells (ng Pt/10⁶ cells); B) Ru/Pt content in cellular DNA expressed as the ng Ru/ μ g DNA (ng Pt/ μ g DNA). A representative experiment is shown.

4.5. Results of morphological analysis of cell death

The morphological characteristics of cell death of PANC-1 cells induced with the investigated complexes and *cisplatin* were analyzed by fluorescent microscopy and acridine orange/ethidium bromide dual staining [64]. After 48 h of treatment with IC_{50} concentrations, the cells started to lose their normal morphology and become rounded, in particular after treatment with complex **3** and *cisplatin* (supplementary Fig. SI1). In case of the other complexes (**2** and **4**), the majority of the cells were still with the morphology like the cells in the control, light green colored and elongated with an epithelial morphology. After 72 h of treatment, the number of cells was reduced compared to the control, again particularly after treatment with complex **3** and *cisplatin* (Fig 6).

Figure 6. Fluorescent micrographs of PANC-1 cells treated with the investigated ruthenium compounds or CDDP at concentrations corresponding to IC_{50} after 72 h treatment. Untreated cells were used as control.

The investigated complexes induced a similar effect on the morphology of cells, i.e. the cells become rounded. Some characteristics of apoptotic morphology are also present, like highly condensed chromatin that is uniformly fluorescent, in the crescents or spherical beads form around the periphery of the nucleus particularly after 72 h treatment. Other morphological characteristics of apoptosis are not present. The majority of cells are with preserved plasma membrane since cells incorporated only AO (green fluorescence). The morphological characteristics of secondary apoptosis and necrosis cells like orange to red colored chromatin, due to disrupted cell membrane in the individual cells are present.

Morphological criteria are often used to define the different types of cell death [65]. According to morphological appearance, cell death can be classified to apoptotic, necrotic, autophagic or associated with mitosis. Moreover, it should be pointed out that the term ‘apoptosis’ hides a major degree of biochemical and functional heterogeneity [66]. Based on our results and having in mind morphological criteria for defining types of cell death, we cannot say for sure what type of cell death is induced by the investigated complexes, but we can emphasize that the integrity of the plasma membrane of the treated cells was preserved, some characteristics of apoptotic morphology are present and that there was no extensive necrosis.

4.6. Analysis of the efficacy of the investigated complexes in the 3D MCTS model

Traditional research on the efficacy of anticancer drugs is usually performed in two-dimensional (2-D) cell cultures, which may not be a true indicator of the *in vivo* effectiveness of cancer treatments. Cells in a 3D culture environment differ morphologically and physiologically from the cells in a 2D culture environment. In the 3D cultures, the spatial organization of the cell surface receptors engaged in interactions with surrounding cells is achieved [66]. The physiological state of spheroids depends on the spheroid size, the individual and cell-type-specific behavior, the cell density, and also the culture time. In contrast to the 2D model systems where the cells are uniformly exposed to oxygen and nutrients, the cells in the 3D model systems are exposed to gradients of chemical and biological signals [67]. Hence, a 3D model, or multicellular tumor spheroids (MCTS) of PANC-1 cancer cells, was introduced in this research to investigate the efficacy of the reported ruthenium complexes on the growth kinetics of MCTSs over a period of time. We

incubated the spheroids for 5 days either with *cisplatin* or investigated ruthenium complexes (2-4). Unlike to their effect in a 2D cell culture, after treatment with complexes 2-4 there was no significant reduction in growth of PANC-1 cells MCTSs. The sizes of the PANC-1 MCTSs which were untreated (control) or treated with the investigated Ru(II) complexes ($2 \times IC_{50}$ concentrations) continuously increased with time (Fig. 7). In contrast, the MCTSs treated with *cisplatin* ($2 \times IC_{50}$ concentration $\sim 30 \mu M$) didn't change in size over time. Their growth is stopped, which becomes evident already after 2 days of treatment. Brightfield images (Fig. 7) show an increase in dark (dead) cells in the center of *cisplatin* treated MCTS. These observations demonstrated that the investigated ruthenium complexes 2-4, although effectively inhibited cell proliferation and killed PANC-1 cancer cells in a 2D cell culture system, even more efficiently than *cisplatin* according to IC_{50} values (see Table 1), were not efficient in a 3D culture model as MCTSs continued to grow.

Figure 7. Growth inhibition monitoring of drug-treated PANC-1 MCTSs. The PANC-1 cells were seeded at a density of 500 cells per well, into low attachment U96-well plate Thermo Scientific Nunclon Sphera. After 5 days of culture (spheroidization time) the PANC-1 MCTS approximately 500 μm in diameter, pre-selected for homogeneous volume and shape, were treated with complexes 2-4 and *cisplatin* (with $2 \times IC_{50}$ concentrations). Brightfield images obtained using an Invitrogen™ EVOS FLC™ imaging system. Scale bar: 1000 μm .

The live/dead viability analysis was performed as a two-color fluorescence staining using Calcein-AM and PI. The non-fluorescent cell-permeant Calcein-AM is converted into green

fluorescent Calcein by intracellular esterases within living cells. In contrast, PI can only enter dead cells and emits red fluorescence upon binding to nucleic acids [42].

Further dual staining of MCTS with Calcein-AM and PI (Fig. 8 and Fig. 9) or with Thermo Fisher Live/Dead (Blue/Green) staining (Figure SI2) confirmed that most of the cells after treatment with the investigated ruthenium complexes were still alive. Complex **3** shows a slightly higher number of dead cells in MCTS of 500 μm diameter, compared to the other two complexes. The spheroids compactness is apparently disturbed, since it appears that the structure of MCTS is distorted (especially around the perimeter) and spheroids gradually decay. While MCTS treated with *cisplatin* totally disintegrated and staining confirmed majority of dead cell. It seems that the spheroid structure was sensitive to the mechanical disturbances caused by addition of dyes (Fig. 7 vs. Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, SI2). When working with MCTS we must consider that an important variable in MCTS is their size since it is correlated with cell function, as well as drug penetration and transport. The various spheroid sizes gives us different information. Smaller spheroids (~ 200 μm) are a good model system to recapitulate cell–cell and cell–matrix interactions but are not large enough to recapitulate oxygen gradients with hypoxic regions or proliferation gradients [68]. The spheroids between 200 and 500 μm are generally sufficiently large to develop gradients of oxygen, nutrients and catabolites [69]. Above a size of 400–600 μm , spheroids develop a central secondary necrosis where the innermost cells die of apoptosis or necrosis [68-70]. Larger spheroids generally have a viable cell rim that is 100–300 μm thick around the necrotic core [70]. Therefore, in our research we treated MCTS with a diameter up to 500 μm (Fig. 7, Fig. 8 and Fig. SI2) and with a diameter over 500 μm (Fig.9). Unfortunately, our results show that the investigated ruthenium complexes (**2-4**) were not efficient in the 3D culture model without distinction based on the size of MCTSs as only disintegration of the spheroids compactness is apparently observed in the spheroids rim in both cases.

A number of studies with DNA damaging drugs as well as with microtubuli interacting agents has shown that when tumor cells are grown as MCTS their sensitivity to anticancer chemotherapeutic drugs generally decreases [43-45, 71].

Figure 8. Calcein-AM (green-live) and PI (red-dead) dual-staining on drug-treated PANC-1 cells MCTSs. The PANC-1 cells were seeded at a density of 500 cells per well, into low attachment U96-well plate Thermo Scientific Nunclon Sphera. After 5 days of culture (spheroidization time) the PANC-1 MCTSs approximately 500 μm in diameter, pre-selected for homogeneous volume and shape, were treated with complexes 1-3 and *cisplatin* ($2 \times \text{IC}_{50}$ concentrations). Presented images were obtained using an Invitrogen™ EVOS FLC™ imaging system. A: bright field; B: Calcein-AM channel; C: PI channel. Scale bar: 1000 μm .

Figure 9. Calcein-AM (green-live) and PI (red-dead) dual-staining on drug-treated PANC-1 cells MCTSs. The PANC-1 cells were seeded at a density of 1000 cells per well, into low attachment U96-well plate Thermo Scientific Nunclon Sphera (Nunclon Sphera 96 well U bottom plates). After 5 days of culture (spheroidization

time) the PANC-1 MCTS aggregates diameter over 500 μ m pre-selected for homogeneous volume and shape were treated with complexes **2-4** and *cisplatin* (2xIC₅₀ concentrations). Presented images were obtained using an Invitrogen™ EVOS FLC™ imaging system. A: bright field; B: Calcein-AM channel; C: PI channel Scale bar: 1000 μ m.

5. Conclusion

The previous study of the mechanism of action of half-sandwich Ru(II)-arene complexes of the type $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{Me}_2\text{dppz})\text{Cl}]\text{PF}_6$, has revealed that this compound acts as strong cytotoxic agent due to an efficient cellular accumulation and its ability to reach and bind nuclear DNA with a much higher affinity than *cisplatin* [42]. Based on these studies, we synthesized a class of novel Ru complexes containing 1,10-phenantroline derivatives to study their structure-activities relationship and reveal the changes in biological activity resulting from small structural modifications of the four Ru(II) complexes. The results of cytotoxicity screening in a 2D model system on the panel of cancer cell lines indicated the high cytotoxicity, even higher than *cisplatin*, with IC₅₀ values ranging from 5 to 9 μ M in *cisplatin* resistant cell lines PANC-1 and MDA-MB-231. Based on the IC₅₀ values we can state that minor changes in dppz ligand, like the introduction of a strongly electron-withdrawing group -NO₂ (**4**) or a weakly electron-withdrawing group -Cl group (**3**) were not sufficient to induce important changes in cytotoxicity, compared to complexes without substituents on the dppz ligand (**2**). As complexes **2-4** had significantly high cytotoxicity in PANC-1 and MDA-MB-231 cells, further investigation of the mechanism of action was necessarily. Studies in a 3D cell culture of multicellular tumor spheroids (MCTS) of PANC-1 cells showed no significant retardation or reduction in growth, after treatment with the investigated ruthenium complexes. Disintegration of the spheroids compactness is observed only in the spheroids rim and majority of the cells is found alive, in contrast to *cisplatin* treatment, which induced retardation in MCTS growth. MCTS treated with *cisplatin*, disintegrated after adding stains, and staining confirmed the majority of dead cells. Having in mind the complexity of a 3D model system and our results further investigations in this model

system are needed, varying time and concentrations, as well as experimental conditions, for more accurate understanding of the effect of the investigated complexes. ICP-MS analysis in PANC-1 cells, revealed surprisingly more efficient cellular uptake of complex **3** compared to complexes **2**, **4** and *cisplatin*. The DNA binding followed the same trend, meaning that concentration of complexes that reached cellular DNA, decreased in the following order: **3** > **2** > **4** < **CDDP**. Still, ICP-MS results did not show clear correlation to the cytotoxic activity of complexes in the present study, as cytotoxicity decreased as following: **2** > **4** > **3** > **CDDP**. We may conclude that higher intracellular accumulation of ruthenium complexes **2-4**, comparing to **CDDP** and higher DNA binding, perhaps by intercalation, certainly contributed to their activity in PANC-1 cells. Additionally, action of **2-4** was devoid of notable cell cycle perturbations. Only complex **3** caused minor cell cycle arrest, characterized by accumulation of cells in the G2-M phase (52.09% vs control 42.01%). Absence of the Sub-G1 phase in cell cycle analysis indicates that there was no fragmentation of DNA. This is a completely different effect of that observed with *cisplatin*, which induced accumulation of cells in the S phase and increase of Sub-G1 phase. Taken together, this study provides important information for further development and investigation of Ru(II)-arene complexes with dipyrrophenazine type ligands, as anticancer agents.

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a)

b)

c)

d)

e)

f)

g)

■ Sub-G1 ■ G1 □ S ■ G2

Control

2

3

4

CDDP

■ Sub-G1 □ G1 □ S ■ G2

1. KBrO_3 , 65% H_2SO_4 , r.t., 24h
2. Na_2CO_3 , pH 7, CHCl_3 , MgSO_4
3. MeOH

1. *o*-Phenylenediamine
or 4-Nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine
or 4-Chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine
2. 96% Ethanol, 30 min
3. MeOH

X= -H or -NO₂ or -Cl

(1)

R=H (2); R=Cl (3); R=NO₂ (4)

Table 1. The cytotoxic activity of complexes **1-4** and *cisplatin* (CDDP) as reference compound determined after 72 h treatment by the MTT assay

Compound	IC ₅₀ (μM)				
	K562	A549	PANC-1	MDA-MB-231	MRC-5
1	6.65±0.07	26.85±7.67	21.26±0.98	7.44±2.75	4.23±0.63
2	6.23±2.26	19.45±3.37	5.49±0.64	5.60±0.03	8.62±3.61
3	6.35±1.51	9.23±1.40	8.47±2.21	9.06±4.48	13.92±4.04
4	6.77±1.86	18.89±2.08	5.66±0.37	5.41±0.57	9.98±1.85
<i>cisplatin</i>	10.86±0.55 ^b	5.93±0.66 ^a	16.44±1.56	14.54±0.05	10.54±0.21

IC₅₀ values were calculated as mean values obtained from two to three independent experiments and presented with their standard deviations. ^aResults of activity previously reported [57] ^bResults of activity previously reported [58]

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) as49

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No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: as49

Bond precision:	C-C = 0.0043 A	Wavelength=0.71073
Cell:	a=14.6663(5) b=11.4594(3) c=13.9648(5)	
	alpha=90 beta=91.810(3) gamma=90	
Temperature:	100 K	
	Calculated	Reported
Volume	2345.85(13)	2345.85(13)
Space group	P 21/c	P 1 21/c 1
Hall group	-P 2ybc	-P 2ybc
Moiety formula	C23 H24 Cl N2 Ru, F6 P	C23 H24 Cl N2 Ru, F6 P
Sum formula	C23 H24 Cl F6 N2 P Ru	C23 H24 Cl F6 N2 P Ru
Mr	609.93	609.93
Dx,g cm-3	1.727	1.727
Z	4	4
Mu (mm-1)	0.913	0.913
F000	1224.0	1224.0
F000'	1220.58	
h,k,lmax	20,16,19	19,16,18
Nref	6696	5864
Tmin,Tmax	0.767,0.928	0.340,1.000
Tmin'	0.721	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.340 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = GAUSSIAN

Data completeness= 0.876 Theta(max)= 29.790

R(reflections)= 0.0433(4356) wR2(reflections)= 0.0925(5864)

S = 1.039 Npar= 311

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● Alert level C

PLAT244_ALERT_4_C	Low 'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	P1	Check
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600	4	Report
PLAT973_ALERT_2_C	Check Calcd Positive Resid. Density on Ru1	1.03	eA-3

● Alert level G

PLAT910_ALERT_3_G	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min).	2	Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600	781	Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G	Number of OMIT Records in Embedded .res File ...	1	Note
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.	1	Info

- 0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
- 0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
- 3 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
- 4 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

- 0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
 - 3 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
 - 2 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
 - 2 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
 - 0 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check
-

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checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) as91

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No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: as91

Bond precision:	C-C = 0.0042 A	Wavelength=0.71073
Cell:	a=20.4806(4) b=20.8770(4) c=13.5030(3)	alpha=90 beta=91.2623(18) gamma=90
Temperature:	100 K	
	Calculated	Reported
Volume	5772.1(2)	5772.1(2)
Space group	P 21/c	P 1 21/c 1
Hall group	-P 2ybc	-P 2ybc
Moiety formula	2(C28 H24 Cl N4 Ru), 2(F6 P), C4 H10 O	2(C28 H24 Cl N4 Ru), 2(F6 P), C4 H10 O
Sum formula	C60 H58 Cl2 F12 N8 O P2 Ru2	C60 H58 Cl2 F12 N8 O P2 Ru2
Mr	1470.12	1470.12
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.692	1.692
Z	4	4
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.762	0.762
F000	2968.0	2968.0
F000'	2961.35	
h,k,lmax	28,29,18	27,28,16
Nref	16309	13952
Tmin,Tmax	0.899,0.930	0.988,0.993
Tmin'	0.885	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.988 Tmax=0.993
AbsCorr = GAUSSIAN

Data completeness= 0.855 Theta(max)= 29.647

R(reflections)= 0.0430(10204) wR2(reflections)= 0.0964(13952)

S = 1.040 Npar= 792

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT220_ALERT_2_C	Large Non-Solvent	C	Ueq(max)/Ueq(min) Range	3.5	Ratio
PLAT244_ALERT_4_C	Low	'Solvent'	Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	P1	Check
PLAT910_ALERT_3_C	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s)	Below Th(Min)	...	9	Report
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing # FCF Refl Between THmin & STh/L=	0.600		7	Report

● **Alert level G**

PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Check Large Av C6-Ring C-C Dist.	C4	-C11	1.43	Ang.
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Check Large Av C6-Ring C-C Dist.	C29	-C34	1.43	Ang.
PLAT380_ALERT_4_G	Incorrectly? Oriented X(sp2)-Methyl Moiety		C28	Check
PLAT432_ALERT_2_G	Short Inter X...Y Contact	F9	.. C51 ..	2.92	Ang.
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L=	0.600		1969	Note
PLAT952_ALERT_5_G	Calculated (ThMax) and CIF-Reported Lmax Differ			2	Units
PLAT958_ALERT_1_G	Calculated (ThMax) and Actual (FCF) Lmax Differ			2	Units

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2 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
3 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
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PLATON version of 19/11/2015; check.def file version of 17/11/2015

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) as59a

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No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: as59a

Bond precision:	C-C = 0.0287 A	Wavelength=1.54184	
Cell:	a=20.1524(6)	b=30.0825(10)	c=13.8149(5)
	alpha=90	beta=90	gamma=90
Temperature:	100 K		
	Calculated	Reported	
Volume	8375.1(5)	8375.1(5)	
Space group	P n c 2	P n c 2	
Hall group	P 2 -2bc	P 2 -2bc	
Moiety formula	C28 H23 Cl2 N4 Ru, F6 P	C28 H23 Cl2 N4 Ru, F6 P	
Sum formula	C28 H23 Cl2 F6 N4 P Ru	C28 H23 Cl2 F6 N4 P Ru	
Mr	732.44	732.44	
Dx,g cm-3	1.743	1.743	
Z	12	12	
Mu (mm-1)	7.461	7.461	
F000	4392.0	4392.0	
F000'	4417.65		
h,k,lmax	25,37,17	25,37,17	
Nref	17497[9132]	14615	
Tmin,Tmax	0.461,0.607	0.696,1.000	
Tmin'	0.231		

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.696 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 1.60/0.84 Theta(max)= 75.970

R(reflections)= 0.0864(12057) wR2(reflections)= 0.2329(14615)

S = 1.053 Npar= 1146

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format
test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.
Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level B

PLAT342_ALERT_3_B	Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds	0.02869	Ang.
PLAT412_ALERT_2_B	Short Intra XH3 .. XHn H50 .. H53C ..	1.79	Ang.
PLAT971_ALERT_2_B	Check Calcd Residual Density 1.15A From C1	2.59	eA-3

Alert level C

STRVA01_ALERT_4_C	Flack test results are ambiguous.		
	From the CIF: _refine_ls_abs_structure_Flack	0.320	
	From the CIF: _refine_ls_abs_structure_Flack_su	0.020	
PLAT090_ALERT_3_C	Poor Data / Parameter Ratio (Zmax > 18)	7.68	Note
PLAT220_ALERT_2_C	Non-Solvent Resd 2 C Ueq(max)/Ueq(min) Range	3.7	Ratio
PLAT220_ALERT_2_C	Non-Solvent Resd 3 C Ueq(max)/Ueq(min) Range	5.3	Ratio
PLAT222_ALERT_3_C	Non-Solvent Resd 3 H Uiso(max)/Uiso(min) Range	5.5	Ratio
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference Ru2 -- C48 ..	0.16	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C73 -- C80 ..	0.18	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference C80 -- C81 ..	0.22	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference P1 -- F2 ..	0.17	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference P3 -- F13 ..	0.23	Ang.
PLAT234_ALERT_4_C	Large Hirshfeld Difference P3 -- F14 ..	0.22	Ang.
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	C80	Check
PLAT362_ALERT_2_C	Short C(sp3)-C(sp2) Bond C45 - C52 ..	1.38	Ang.
PLAT601_ALERT_2_C	Structure Contains Solvent Accessible VOIDS of .	43	Ang3
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing # FCF Refl Between THmin & STh/L=	0.600	8 Report
PLAT915_ALERT_3_C	No Flack x Check Done: Low Friedel Pair Coverage	69	%
PLAT971_ALERT_2_C	Check Calcd Residual Density 0.66A From Ru2	1.84	eA-3
PLAT971_ALERT_2_C	Check Calcd Residual Density 0.45A From Ru3	1.57	eA-3
PLAT972_ALERT_2_C	Check Calcd Residual Density 0.74A From Ru1	-1.55	eA-3
PLAT977_ALERT_2_C	Check the Negative Difference Density on H24A	-0.35	eA-3
PLAT977_ALERT_2_C	Check the Negative Difference Density on H53B	-0.38	eA-3

Alert level G

PLAT003_ALERT_2_G	Number of Uiso or Uij Restrained non-H Atoms ...	127	Report
PLAT072_ALERT_2_G	SHELXL First Parameter in WGHT Unusually Large	0.11	Report
PLAT083_ALERT_2_G	SHELXL Second Parameter in WGHT Unusually Large	59.19	Why ?
PLAT186_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains ISOR Records	1	Report
PLAT187_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains RIGU Records	1	Report
PLAT244_ALERT_4_G	Low 'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	P1	Check
PLAT244_ALERT_4_G	Low 'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	P2	Check
PLAT244_ALERT_4_G	Low 'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	P3	Check
PLAT244_ALERT_4_G	Low 'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	P4	Check
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Check Large Av C6-Ring C-C Dist. C1 -C5	1.43	Ang.
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Check Large Av C6-Ring C-C Dist. C18 -C23	1.43	Ang.
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Check Large Av C6-Ring C-C Dist. C027 -C41	1.42	Ang.
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Check Large Av C6-Ring C-C Dist. C55 -C72	1.43	Ang.
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Check Large Av C6-Ring C-C Dist. C73 -C78	1.42	Ang.
PLAT432_ALERT_2_G	Short Inter X...Y Contact F7 .. C47 ..	2.91	Ang.
PLAT432_ALERT_2_G	Short Inter X...Y Contact F7 .. C46 ..	2.93	Ang.
PLAT432_ALERT_2_G	Short Inter X...Y Contact C22 .. C22 ..	3.11	Ang.
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G	Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels	2	Note
PLAT722_ALERT_1_G	Angle Calc 118.00, Rep 119.10 Dev...	1.10	Degree
	C48 -C47 -H47 1.555 1.555 1.555 #	274	Check
PLAT860_ALERT_3_G	Number of Least-Squares Restraints	2086	Note
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min)	3	Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L=	0.600	314 Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G	Number of OMIT Records in Embedded .res File ...	8	Note
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.	1	Note

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Publication of your CIF in other journals

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Supplementary material to:

Antitumor activity of organoruthenium complexes with chelate aromatic ligands, derived from 1,10-phenantroline: synthesis and biological activity

Aleksandar Savić, *University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia.*

Nevenka Gligorijević, *Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, Pasterova 14, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

Sandra Arandelović, *Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, Pasterova 14, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

Biljana Dojčinović, *Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade, Njegoševa 12, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

Anna M. Kaczmarek, *L³-Luminescent Lanthanide Lab, Ghent University, Department of Chemistry, B-9000 Ghent, Belgium*

Siniša Radulović, *Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, Pasterova 14, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

Rik Van Deun, *L³-Luminescent Lanthanide Lab, Ghent University, Department of Chemistry, B-9000 Ghent, Belgium*

Kristof Van Hecke, *XStruct, Ghent University, Department of Chemistry, B-9000 Ghent, Belgium.*

Biology

Figure S11. Fluorescent micrographs of PANC-1 cells treated with the investigated ruthenium compounds or CDDP at concentrations corresponding to IC_{50} after 48 h treatment. Untreated cells were used as control.

Figure S12. The Thermo Fisher Live/Dead (Blue/Green) staining of drug-treated PANC-1 cells MCTSs. The PANC-1 cells were seeded at a density of 500 cells per well, into low attachment U96-well plate Thermo Scientific Nunclon Sphera. After 5 days of culture (spheroidization time) the PANC-1 MCTS approximately 500 μm in diameter, pre-selected for homogeneous volume and shape, were treated with complexes 1-3 and cisplatin ($2 \times IC_{50}$ concentrations). Presented images were obtained using an Invitrogen™ EVOS FLC™ imaging system. A: bright field; B: Blue-live cells; C: Green-dead cells. Scale bar: 1000 μm .

Crystallography

For the structures of **1-3**, X-ray intensity data were collected at 100 K, on a Rigaku Oxford Diffraction Supernova Dual Source (Cu at zero) diffractometer equipped with an Atlas CCD detector using ω scans and $MoK\alpha$ ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) and $CuK\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.54184 \text{ \AA}$) radiation, for **1** and **2**, and **3**, respectively. The images were interpreted and integrated with the program CrysAlisPro [1]. Using Olex2 [2], the structure was solved by direct methods using the ShelXS structure solution program and refined by full-matrix least-squares on F^2 using the ShelXL

program package [3,4]. Non-hydrogen atoms were anisotropically refined and the hydrogen atoms in the riding mode and isotropic temperature factors fixed at 1.2 times $U(\text{eq})$ of the parent atoms (1.5 times for methyl groups).

Crystal data for compound 1. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{ClF}_6\text{N}_2\text{PRu}$, $M = 609.93$, monoclinic, space group $P2_1/c$ (No. 14), $a = 14.6663(5) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 11.4594(3) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 13.9648(5) \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 91.810(3)^\circ$, $V = 2345.85(13) \text{ \AA}^3$, $Z = 4$, $T = 100 \text{ K}$, $\rho_{\text{calc}} = 1.727 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, $\mu(\text{Cu-K}\alpha) = 0.913 \text{ mm}^{-1}$, $F(000) = 1224$, 26909 reflections measured, 5864 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0584$) which were used in all calculations. The final $R1$ was 0.0433 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and $wR2$ was 0.0925 (all data).

Crystal data for compound 2. $\text{C}_{60}\text{H}_{58}\text{Cl}_2\text{F}_{12}\text{N}_8\text{OP}_2\text{Ru}_2$, $M = 1470.12$, monoclinic, space group $P2_1/c$ (No. 14), $a = 20.4806(4) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 20.8770(4) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 13.5030(3) \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 91.2623(18)^\circ$, $V = 5772.1(2) \text{ \AA}^3$, $Z = 4$, $T = 100 \text{ K}$, $\rho_{\text{calc}} = 1.692 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, $\mu(\text{Cu-K}\alpha) = 0.762 \text{ mm}^{-1}$, $F(000) = 2968$, 59331 reflections measured, 13952 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0624$) which were used in all calculations. The final $R1$ was 0.0430 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and $wR2$ was 0.0964 (all data).

Crystal data for compound 3. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{23}\text{Cl}_2\text{F}_6\text{N}_4\text{P Ru}$, $M = 732.44$, orthorhombic, space group $Pnc2$ (No. 30), $a = 20.1524(6) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 30.0825(10) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 13.8149(5) \text{ \AA}$, $V = 8375.1(5) \text{ \AA}^3$, $Z = 12$, $T = 100 \text{ K}$, $\rho_{\text{calc}} = 1.743 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, $\mu(\text{Cu-K}\alpha) = 7.461 \text{ mm}^{-1}$, $F(000) = 4392$, 34425 reflections measured, 14615 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0622$) which were used in all calculations. The final $R1$ was 0.0864 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and $wR2$ was 0.2329 (all data).

CCDC 1903330-1903332 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper and can be obtained free of charge via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html (or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12, Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; fax: +44-1223-336033; or deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

[1] Rigaku Oxford Diffraction (2015). CrysAlisPro Software system, Rigaku Corporation, Oxford, UK.

[2] O.V. Dolomanov, L.J. Bourhis, R.J. Gildea, J.A.K. Howard, H. Puschmann, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 42 (2009) 339-341.

[3] G.M. Sheldrick, *Acta Crystallogr. Sect. A* 64 (2008) 112-122.

[4] G.M. Sheldrick, *Acta Crystallogr. Sect. C* 71 (2015) 3-8.

Figure S13. Asymmetric unit of the crystal structure of **1**, showing thermal displacement ellipsoids at the 50% probability level.

Figure SI4. Asymmetric unit of the crystal structure of **2**, showing thermal displacement ellipsoids at the 50% probability level.

Figure S15. Asymmetric unit of the crystal structure of **3**, showing thermal displacement ellipsoids at the 30% probability level.

NMR spectra of complexes

Figure SI6. ^1H NMR of complex 1.

Figure SI7. ^1H NMR of complex **2**.

Figure SI8. ^1H NMR of complex **3**.

Figure SI9. ^1H NMR of complex 4.